

Assessing the Impact of E-HRM on Organisational Performance: An Empirical Study

¹Dr. Mahmoud Mohamed Elsaywy,²Dr. Mohamed Ahmed Elbadawi Ali

¹Assistant Professor, City University Collage of Ajman, UAE & Assistant Professor, Sadat academy for management sciences, Cairo, Egypt

²Assistant Professor, City University Collage of Ajman, UAE

* Corresponding author: dr.elsawy@hotmail.com

Received: 07th July 2021

Revised: 21st August 2021

Accepted: 03rd September 2021

Abstract: The goal of the research was to assess the impact of e-Human Resource Management (E-HRM) on organizational performance. There were six independent variables (e-Recruitment & Selection, e-Learning & Training, e-performance appraisal, e-Communication, e-compensation management, and e-Productivity) identified from an in-depth literature review and a conceptual framework to assess the impact of E-HRM on organizational performance was proposed. Data was gathered through the use of a self-structured questionnaire from 241 a wide range of firms' employees in the United Arab Emirates and was analyzed using SPSS version 22.0. A multiple regression was done to predict the organizational performance from all six independent factors. The finding reveals that there is statistically significant positive connection between organizational performance and e-HRM indicators.

As a result, it is recommended that there should be a list of standards for every industry in the United Arab Emirates and automated e-HR processes that contribute to increased productivity and improved organizational performance.

Key words: multiple regression, United Arab Emirates, e-HR, performance appraisal

1. Introduction

Many organisational departments have undergone functionality adjustments to improve their efficacy and performance since the dawn of the Information Technology (IT) revolution. Many firms have incorporated information technology (IT) into their operations in an effort to boost productivity. IT transformation also comes at a time when corporate markets have shrunk, and many organisations are seeking refuge in other markets because of globalisation. A important pillar in an organization's structure, human resource management has adapted to global business trends and used information technology to increase its performance and efficiency, as noted by Ma and Ye (2015).

Electronic human resource management incorporates a wide range of internet-based technologies and protocol systems to streamline human resource operations. For the time being, e-HRM can be used for transactional activities, such as recruiting, selection, training, compensation and performance management, and also for transformational activities that add value to the organisation. It can also be used to manage HR throughout an employee's entire career, from hiring to retirement. Self-service systems, made possible by web-based technology, now allow companies to give services to employees and managers directly. e-HRM has the added benefit of increasing the value of the organisation.

The usage of e-HRM techniques has grown in popularity all around the world. In order to achieve a specific degree of efficiency and effectiveness, the majority of enterprises, primarily multinational firms, have implemented a digital HR management system. Bondarouk, Parry, and Furtmueller (2017) report that e-HRM has been embraced to varying degrees by most companies in Europe and the United States.

In isolation, all of the characteristics of E-efficacy HRM's and contribution to organisational performance can be examined. There are several practises in electronic human resources management, according to the author Geetha (2017). These practises include electronic performance appraisal, electronic recruitment and selection, electronic compensation management, electronic surveillance, electronic attendance, electronic time management and electronic leave administration. Study focused on six HR practises: e-Recruitment and selection, learning and training, performance appraisal and communication. It also looked at how remuneration is managed electronically. And finally, it looked at how employees' productivity electronically.

2. Literature Review

2.1 E-HRM

According to Lengnick & Mortiz (2003), E-HRM is at the core of any technology used to support the delivery of human resources services. For Marler (2009), E-HRM is a technology-based approach where procedures and personnel are aligned with the organization's goals through the use of integrated technology. In the last ten years, E-HRM has gotten a lot of attention. It's a catch-all word for all potential HRM-IT integration processes and contents aimed at providing value for targeted employees and management in and across enterprises. HR transactional costs and HR headcount can be reduced with e-HRM, according to Martin et al (2008a).

2.2 E-HRM Dimensions

2.2.1 E-Recruitment

E-recruitment makes considerable use of digital and web-based technology to help in the hiring process (Ahmed, 2019). Today, practically every company uses a variety of internet sites to find new employees, either directly or via a third party. Job openings are advertised on a variety of internet channels, and candidates can apply electronically and upload their resumes to save money and time (Patel & Dhal,2017). The systems then assign a numerical ranking to each applicant based on a variety of factors, such as education, work experience, GPA, and so on. Fuzu, Relief Web International, and Brighter Monday are just a few of the third-party e-recruitment services employed by the organisation in Kenya to find new employees.

Electronic selection, or E-Selection, is a paperless method of selecting applications that makes use of sophisticated computer systems. It includes online testing, evaluating resumes, and conducting interviews where recruiters can gauge a candidate's skill set and suitability for the position (Stone et al, 2015). For entry-level positions, several companies use online aptitude exams, which are followed by a video conferencing interview. Because there is no paperwork to complete, the transaction can be completed at any time of the day or night. Organizations, on the other hand, are pushing for tools like Zoom, which provide superior audio and video quality for applicant interviews (Parker, 2014).

H1: 'E-Recruitment & selection' factor has a significant impact on 'Organisational Performance'.

2.2.2 E-Learning & Training

When it comes to e-learning and training, digital technology is used to provide access to knowledge at any time and from any location. It also requires sharing information on an on-going basis without regard for time or resource constraints (Geetha, 2017). Virtual classrooms, self-placed learning modules, web conferencing, and professional networking are some of the techniques employed in the training process. With huge corporations increasingly going global, e-learning has emerged as the best method for delivering training and education. It also improved the efficiency of organisations and the flexibility of their personnel while also decreasing both costs and time (Miller, 2012).

Many aspects of e-training are similar to those of e-learning, such as the methods of delivery employed and the technology involved, but the time span for learning is significantly shorter, and it is frequently tailored to meet a specific learning target or skill set (Ramayah, et al., 2012).

H2: 'E-Learning & Training' factor has a significant impact on 'Organisational Performance'.

2.2.3 E-Performance appraisal

When employees are evaluated online for their ability to perform to expectations in their job descriptions, it is known as an E-Performance Appraisal (EPA). According to research, firms utilise e-Performance appraisal to assess employee performance and provide feedback (Cedar Crestone, 2014). One of the HR activities is performance appraisal, which is frequently done on an ongoing basis. Organizations can drastically minimise the workload and time required to conduct a performance review by utilising digital technology. Managers can also use IT systems to connect the organization's goals, plans, and practises with the performance management programme. Top performers across the company can be identified with the help of E-Performance, which keeps and motivates top employees (Jarrar and Schiuma, 2007).

H3: 'E-Performance appraisal' factor has a significant impact on 'Organisational Performance'.

2.2.4 E-Compensation

Using software approaches to model employee remuneration structures and cash and no-cash compensation plans to strategically drive organisational success is called e-compensation (Stone et al, 2015). Employee retention is greatly improved when managers use an online pay practise to generate compensation reports for their staff on-the-fly. As a result, the workforce is more adaptable. Automating and creating

compensation systems has reduced administrative expenses and time, allowing the organisation to be more adaptable (SHRM, 2007).

H4: 'E- Compensation' factor has a significant impact on 'Organisational Performance'.

2.2.5 E-Communication

The HRM system includes e-communication, and prior to that, all mail was delivered by mail. As we move to physically scattered but digitally connected workplaces, e-communication is becoming increasingly important for communicating and exchanging information. Email's advantages and productivity gains have been thoroughly documented in academic research (Abodohoui, et al., 2014).

H5: 'E- Communication' factor has a significant impact on 'Organisational Performance'.

2.2.6 E-Productivity

If staff are capable of completing tasks on time, within the required quantity and quality standards, and in a manner that best meets the expectations of customers and the firm in terms of predicted long-term production, productivity and quality of services or goods are described as a function. Employee productivity measures how well a company's employees create output in order to meet a specific goal (Iqbal, Ahmed & Borini, 2019). E-HRM offers employees the chance to develop their skills and productivity while doing it in a more pleasant manner and with less time spent on it. According to the findings of this study, implementing e-HRM practises could increase employee productivity while also requiring less work on their part (Huang et al., 2004).

H6: 'E-Productivity' factor has a significant impact on 'Organisational Performance'.

2.2.7 Organizational Performance

As an organization's ability to satisfy expectations and desired long-term and short-term goals is measured by consistently registering earnings (for profit-making organisations) and properly resolving inherent business uncertainties, organisational performance can be defined (Roman et al., 2012). The ability of a company to outperform its own expectations is a competitive advantage and a long-term performance indicator linked to a variety of financial, production, and market development aspects.

2.3 E-HRM and Organizational Performance

These findings show that using e-HRM can improve the value of HR and also increase HR's ability to contribute competitive advantage through improved efficiency and effectiveness, along with a greater part in carrying the commercial tactic. The relationship between e-HRM use as well as actual organizational performance shows this potential (Al.Hazi, 2019). Due to e-effect HRM's on the organization's enactment, metrics or performance indicators have been adopted without conceptual examination with what to monitor, just how these metrics are established, or why they would be picked. There have also been just a few studies on the impact of HRM on a company's performance measures, particularly for those positioned at the divisional level (Oladele and Omotayo, 2014). According to a comprehensive analysis of the literature, research into e-HRM systems is still in its infancy.

This research contributes in a number of ways. e-impact HRM's on organisational performance will be examined in this study, adding to the body of knowledge. The model that has been proposed can be put to the test diagonally in all areas. Furthermore, the results of this research show how effective the e-HRM system is at improving organisational performance in the United Arab Emirates.

3. Research Objectives

The goal of this research is to discover how E-HRM aspects relate to organisational performance. The following are the study's primary goals:

- To study the concept of E-HRM in general and in the specific context of Organisational Performance
- To identify the variables related to E-HRM in the specific context of Organisational Performance
- To propose a conceptual framework linking E-HRM practice towards organizational performance and
- To empirically validate the proposed framework linking E-HRM practice towards organizational performance

4. Conceptual Model

Figure 1 depicts the link between E-HRM practise and organisational performance. Figure 1. Conceptual framework.

Fig 1: Conceptual framework showing relationship among E-HRM dimensions and of organizational performance

5. Research Methodology

There are two sections to the questionnaire: In the first section, respondents were asked about their demographics. The second section asked about their thoughts on the link between EHRM characteristics

and organisational performance. The assertions are rated on a Likert scale of 1 to 5, with 1 denoting strong agreement and 5 denoting strong disagreement.

Sample Design: It was a convenience sample that was used in this study of respondents (managers, senior executives, junior executives, and supervisors) from various organisations in the United Arab Emirates. A total of 295 questionnaires were distributed, with 241 being fully completed. A response rate of 81.69 percent was discovered after careful examination, which is considered excellent. According to the descriptive data, there were 241 men and women in the final sample.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics: Summary Statistics of the Population

		Frequency	Valid %			Frequency	Valid %
Gender Profile	Male	206	85.5	Marital Status	Married	213	88.4
	Female	35	14.5		Un-Married	28	11.6
Age Profile	21-29 years	32	13.3	Monthly Income	AED.1-5 thousands	62	25.7
	30-39 years	70	29.0		AED.6-10 thousands	85	35.3
	40-49 years	45	18.7		AED.11-15 thousands	64	26.6
	46-55 years	58	24.1		AED. 16-20 thousands	14	5.8
	60 Years and older	36	14.9		More than -AED 20 thousands	16	6.6
Highest Education Level	Diploma/ 10+2	30	12.4	Current Designation	managers	63	26.1
	Bachelor Degree	64	26.6		Executive	84	34.9
	Master Degree	103	42.7		Supervisors	78	32.4
	Professional Education	44	18.3		Others	16	6.6
Length of Affiliation	1-2 years	53	22.0				
	3-5 years	83	34.4				
	6-10 years	90	37.3				
	11 years and more	15	6.2				

6. Results and Discussion

The data was analysed with SPSS version 22. In order to establish construct validity and Cronbach alpha to check internal consistency, the study makes use of the exploratory factor analysis method. The potential associations between the variables were discovered using the regression approach.

PCA (Principal Component Analysis) was used for conforming constructs in the EFA (Exploratory Factor Analysis). Hair et al. (1998) state that factor loading more than or equal to 0.30 is deemed to meet the lowest level; factor loading greater or equal to 0.40 is considered relevant; factor loading greater or equal to 0.50 is considered extremely significant. A factor loading of 0.50 was utilised as a stopping point for this study.

Table 2 shows the findings of the factor analysis. KMO A component analysis is beneficial for data if the value is between 0.5 and 1.0.. The sphere city test by Bartlett reveals the degree of interdependence between the variables. When determining the test's significance level, researchers can learn the outcome. There are likely significant correlations between the variables when the values are very small (less than 0.05). If the p-value is larger than .10, the data may not be suitable for a factor analysis to be performed on them. They show that factor analysis is appropriate for this set of data. No item had a loading lower than 0.5, hence all twenty-one items were confirmed for final analysis.

Macro Variable	Micro Variable	Factor loadings	KMO Measure of Sample Adequacy (>0.5)	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		Items confirmed	Items dropped	Cum % of loading
				Chi Square	Sig. (<.10)			
E-HRM	E-Recruitment & Selection -1	.907	.574	211.429	.000	3	0	65.843
	E-Recruitment & Selection -2	.843						
	E-Recruitment & Selection -3	.665						
	E-Learning & Training -1	.878	.705	355.625	.000	3	0	78.536
	E-Learning & Training -2	.857						
	E-Learning & Training -3	.922						
	E-performance appraisal -1	.737	.642	309.165	.000	3	0	72.860
	E-performance appraisal -2	.901						
	E-performance appraisal -3	.912						
	E-Communication -1	.822	.628	120.772	.000	3	0	60.684
	E-Communication -2	.826						
	E-Communication -3	.681						
	E-Compensation-1	.979	.691	1386.834	.000	3	0	90.467
	E-Compensation-2	.895						
	E-Compensation-3	.977						
	E-Productivity -1	.794	.651	142.722	.000	3	0	63.612
	E-Productivity -2	.748						
	E-Productivity -3	.848						
	Otganisational Performance-1	.872	.706	248.604	.000	3	0	72.884
	Otganisational Performance -2	.868						
	Otganisational Performance -3	.820						

6.1 Reliability Analysis

The questionnaire's internal consistency was established by computing Chronbach Alpha to determine its dependability. A lower alpha value is acceptable for new scales, according to Nunally and Bernstein (1994), who recommend using an alpha value as low as 0.60. Otherwise, the requirement of an internally consistent established scale with an alpha value of 0.70 is frequently used. The study's Cronbach's alpha cutoff value is 0.7.

Table 3: Results of the Reliability Examination

	Independent Variable	Cronbach Alpha
1	E-Recruitment & Selection	.722
2	E-Learning & Training	.861
3	E-performance appraisal	.808
4	E-Communication	.669
5	E-Compensation	.946
6	E-Productivity	.714
7	Organisational Performance	.813
Over all Reliability of the Questionnaire		.938

Table 3's Cronbach's alpha values are over the cutoff value of 0.7, which is acceptable. With a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.938, the questionnaire's overall reliability is demonstrated.

6.2 Correlation Analysis

The results of the independent variable correlation study show that there is a strong link between all of them. The entire variable has a significant correlation with each of the six variables examined. All six independent variables in "EHRM's" six factors have a substantial association with one another (Refer Table 4). Correlation between "e-performance appraisal" and "e-Recruitment & Selection" is the highest (0.806), while "E-Learning & Training" and "e-Recruitment & Selection" have the least significant relationships (0.308).

Table 4: Correlations

	ERES	EPA	ECOM	ECMPSN	ELT	EPRTY
e-Recruitment & Selection (ERES)	1					
e-performance appraisal (EPA)	.806**	1				
e-Communication (ECOM)	.755**	.798**	1			
e-compensation management (ECMPSN)	.757**	.768**	.723**	1		
E-Learning & Training (ELT)	.308**	.348**	.343**	.367**	1	
E-productivity (EPRTY)	.642**	.744**	.673**	.691**	.313**	1
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

6.3 Regression Analysis

The predictor-criterion relationship between the dependent and independent variables is established using stepwise regression analysis. It was done to see if there was a link between EHRM variables and organisational performance.

6.3.1 Results of Hypotheses Testing for Organisational Performance as Dependent Variable

A number of separate regression models are developed and tested for the Organisational Performance as dependent variable. Six EHRM factors i.e., e-Recruitment & Selection (ERES), e-performance appraisal (EPA), e-Communication (ECOM), e-compensation management (ECMPSN), E-Learning & Training (ELT) and E-productivity (EPRTY) are separately taken as independent variables in regression models with Organisational Performance in UAE as dependent variable as depicted in Figure 1.

According to the results of the step-wise regression analysis in Table 5a and 5b, six factors (e-Recruitment and Selection, e-performance appraisal, e-communication, E-Learning & Training, E-productivity, and e-compensation) were found to be significant predictors of "Organisational Performance." Using the R square of 0.934, we can see that these six variables are capable of explaining "Organisational Performance" to the degree of 93.4 percent in the data in Table 5(a). According to Table 5(b), the "ANOVA results for the regression model are provided, demonstrating validity at the 95 percent confidence level." A brief overview of the corresponding coefficients in Table 5(c) provides beta values of "e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management, E-Learning & Training, e-Communication, E-productivity and e-Recruitment & Selection" Factors as 0.129, 0.221, 0.215, 0.265, 0.195 and 0.164 correspondingly, the results of which are fairly indicative of their significance on "Organisational Performance".

Table 5 (a) Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.863 ^a	.744	.743	.355
2	.911 ^b	.830	.829	.290
3	.936 ^c	.876	.874	.248
4	.955 ^d	.912	.910	.210
5	.962 ^e	.926	.925	.192
6	.967 ^f	.934	.932	.182

- a. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal
- b. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management
- c. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management, E-Learning & Training
- d. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management, E-Learning & Training, e-Communication
- e. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management, E-Learning & Training, e-Communication, E-productivity
- f. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management, E-Learning & Training, e-Communication, E-productivity, e-Recruitment & Selection

Table 5 (b) ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	87.776	1	87.776	696.150	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.135	239	.126		
	Total	117.911	240			
2	Regression	97.885	2	48.943	581.674	.000 ^c
	Residual	20.026	238	.084		
	Total	117.911	240			
3	Regression	103.276	3	34.425	557.490	.000 ^d
	Residual	14.635	237	.062		
	Total	117.911	240			
4	Regression	107.488	4	26.872	608.429	.000 ^e
	Residual	10.423	236	.044		
	Total	117.911	240			
5	Regression	109.232	5	21.846	591.557	.000 ^f
	Residual	8.679	235	.037		
	Total	117.911	240			
6	Regression	110.145	6	18.358	553.176	.000 ^g
	Residual	7.765	234	.033		
	Total	117.911	240			

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal

c. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management

d. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management, E-Learning & Training

e. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management, E-Learning & Training, e-Communication

f. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management, E-Learning & Training, e-Communication, E-productivity

g. Predictors: (Constant), e-performance appraisal, e-compensation management, E-Learning & Training, e-Communication, E-productivity, e-Recruitment & Selection

Table 5 (c) Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.498	.087		5.752	.000
	e-performance appraisal	.800	.030	.863	26.385	.000
2	(Constant)	.517	.071		7.310	.000
	e-performance appraisal	.475	.039	.512	12.280	.000
	e-compensation management	.325	.030	.457	10.961	.000
3	(Constant)	.215	.069		3.124	.002
	e-performance appraisal	.440	.033	.475	13.217	.000
	e-compensation management	.284	.026	.400	11.055	.000
	E-Learning & Training	.183	.020	.231	9.343	.000
4	(Constant)	.156	.058		2.663	.008
	e-performance appraisal	.262	.034	.283	7.811	.000
	e-compensation management	.224	.023	.316	9.928	.000
	E-Learning & Training	.171	.017	.216	10.310	.000
	e-Communication	.271	.028	.328	9.765	.000
5	(Constant)	.074	.055		1.358	.176
	e-performance appraisal	.185	.033	.199	5.655	.000
	e-compensation management	.191	.021	.268	8.965	.000
	E-Learning & Training	.168	.015	.212	11.045	.000
	e-Communication	.250	.026	.302	9.758	.000
	E-productivity	.173	.025	.191	6.873	.000
6	(Constant)	.034	.052		.640	.523
	e-performance appraisal	.120	.033	.129	3.593	.000
	e-compensation management	.157	.021	.221	7.437	.000
	E-Learning & Training	.170	.014	.215	11.793	.000
	e-Communication	.219	.025	.265	8.771	.000
	E-productivity	.177	.024	.195	7.379	.000
	e-Recruitment & Selection	.139	.026	.164	5.246	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational Performance

7. Test Results for Hypotheses

Within the conceptual framework of the study, An initial set of fifteen hypotheses was put forward and Table 6 shows that all of the items in this category have been approved.

Table 6: Summary of Test Results for Hypotheses

Assessing the Impact of E-HRM on Organisational Performance: An Empirical Study

H y. N o.	Independent Variables	to	Dependent Variables	R-Squar e	Beta Coefficie nt	t-value	Sig Value	Status of Hypothese s
H 1	E-performance appraisal	→	Organisational Performance (ORGP)	0.934	.129	3.593	0.000	Accepted
H 2	E-compensation management	→	Organisational Performance (ORGP)		.221	7.437	0.000	Accepted
H 3	E-Learning & Training	→	Organisational Performance (ORGP)		.215	11.793	0.000	Accepted
H 4	E-Communication	→	Organisational Performance (ORGP)		.265	8.771	0.000	Accepted
H 5	E-productivity	→	Organisational Performance (ORGP)		.195	7.379	0.000	Accepted
H 6	E-Recruitment & Selection	→	Organisational Performance (ORGP)		.164	5.246	0.000	Accepted

8. Conclusion

this study was conducted to further understand how the e-HRM system affects organisational results. EHRM characteristics were evaluated in connection to organisational performance using six independent variables and one dependent variable. The results indicated that all the six dimensions of E-HRM are significant predictor of “Organisational Performance”. As a result, the findings of this study show that the EHRM dimensions and organisational performance are positively associated.

In order to keep the right balance between personal and organisational goals, an effective e-HRM system is necessary. There is potential for expanding this research to include every industry to better understand the problems organisations and people experience when implementing an electronic human resources management system and the resulting impact on organisational performance.

9. Limitations & Recommendations

Only a few industries were studied, so the framework could be tested in other industries as well to increase the framework's generalization ability. It was decided to focus on just six different variables to see how e-HRM impacts organisational performance .but Future research could include a few more variables that could have a greater impact. The data was gathered through the technique of convenience sampling instead of using a random sampling. Therefore, Considerable care needs to be taken when generalising the

findings. The number of people that participated in the study (n=241) was also limited. A more representative sample drawn from a wider population may yield more conclusive results.

REFERENCES

- Abodohou, A., Mohiuddin, M., & Su, Z. (2014). E-communication adoption in Benin Public Administration: Challenges and strategies. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(1), 43
- Ahmed, M. T. (2019). E-HRM Practices and its impact on Organizational Performance: A study on the Manufacturing industry in Bangladesh
- Al Hazi, M. (2019). Implementing e-Human Resource Management for Improving Organizational Performance: A Conceptual Framework in the Oman Context. *Proceedings of the European Conference on Management, Leadership & Governance*, 11-16. <https://doi.org/10.34190/MLG.19.134>
- Bondarouk, T. V., & Ruel, H. J. M. (2009). Electronic human resource management: Challenges in the digital era. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20(3), 505-514
- Bondarouk, T., Parry, E., & Furtmueller, E. (2017). Electronic HRM: four decades of research on adoption and consequences. *The International Journal of human resource management*, 28(1), 98-131
- Cedar Crestone (2014). CedarCrestone 2013-2014 HR Systems Survey HR Technologies, Deployment Approaches, Value, and Metrics 16th Annual. Retrieved May 15, 2014
- Geetha, R. (2017). Multi-Dimensional Perspective of e-HRM: A Diagnostic Study of Select Auto-Component Firms. *Dharana-Bhavan's International Journal of Business*, 8(2), 60-72
- Huang, J. -H., Jin, B. -H. & Yang, C. (2004). Satisfaction with business-to-employee benefit systems and organizational citizenship behavior: An examination of gender differences. *International Journal of Manpower*, 25(2), 195-210.
- Iqbal, N., Ahmad, M., Raziq, M., & Borini, F. (2019). Linking e-hrm practices and organizational outcomes: empirical analysis of line manager's perception [Ebook] (21st ed., pp. 48-69). São Paulo: Review of Business Management. Retrieved from <http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rbgn/v21n1/1983-0807>
- Jarrar Y, Schiuma G (2007). Measuring performance in the public sector: challenges and trends. *Meas. Bus. Excell.*, 11(4): 4-8
- Lengnick-Hall M.L. and Moritz, S., (2003). The impact of e-HR on the human resource management function. *Journal of Labour Research*, 24(3): 365 - 37
- Martin, G., Reddington, M., & Alexander, H. (2008). Technology, outsourcing and HR transformation: An introduction. *Technology, outsourcing and transforming HR*, 1-37

Assessing the Impact of E-HRM on Organisational Performance: An Empirical Study

- Miller, L. (2012). ASTD 2012 State of the Industry Report: Organizations Continue to Invest in Workplace Learning. *Training & Development Magazine*, 66, 42-48
- Oladele, I. O. and Omotayo, O. A. (2014) „e-Human Resource Management and Organizational Performance (e- HRM) in the Nigerian Banking Industry: An Empirical Study of Guaranty Trust Bank Plc (GTBank)“, *Anvesha*, 7(1), 10-20
- Patel & Dhal (2017). *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication* , 5 (2), 5
- Ramayah, T., Ahmad, N. H., & Tan, S. H. (2012). An Assessment of E-training Effectiveness in Multinational Companies in Malaysia. *Educational Technology & Society*, 15(2), 125-137
- Roman, D. J., Piana, J., e Leal, M. A. S. P., de Mello, N. R., & Erdmann, R. H. (2012). Organizational competitiveness factors. *Brazilian Business Review*, 9(1), 25-42
- Stone, D. L., Deadrick, D. L., Lukaszewski, K. M., & Johnson, R. (2015). The influence of technology on the future of human resource management. *Human Resource Management Review*, 25(2), 216-231
- Thite, M. O. H. A. N., Kavanagh, M. J., & Johnson, R. D. (2012). Evolution of human resource management and human resource information systems. *Introduction to Human Resource Management*, 2-34